

List of 31 New IRRI- NARES Varieties for India

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1. INTRODUCTION

Rice is a staple crop critical to India's food security, yet its production is increasingly challenged by climate variability, water scarcity, and evolving consumer demands. In response, the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), in collaboration with India's National Agricultural Research and Extension System (NARES), has developed and released 31 high-performing rice varieties, officially notified in the Gazette of India in 2024, for large-scale cultivation across diverse rice-growing ecologies.

These varieties were selected for their high yield potential, stress tolerance, and adaptability to both transplanted and direct-seeded systems. They provide farmers with options for efficient rice cultivation under different agro-ecological conditions while meeting quality and nutritional requirements.

2. LIST OF NEW IRRI-NARES VARIETIES

Variety Name	Ecology	Yield (kg/ha) / Stress Yield	Duration (Days)	Grain Type	Recommended States / Regions	Special Trait	Developed By
Chandragiri	Early Transplanted	4200	105	Short bold	Odisha, Bihar, West Bengal	–	OUAT, Bhubaneswar
CO 58	Irrigated Mid-Early	5800	120–125	Long slender	Tamil Nadu	–	TNAU, Coimbatore
CR Dhan 108	Early Direct-Seeded	3446	110–114	Medium slender	Odisha, Bihar	–	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 211	Aerobic	5500	114–118	Long slender	Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Chhattisgarh	Wide adaptability	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 212	Aerobic	5700	110–113	Long bold	Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand	Non-lodging; moderately drought tolerant	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 214	Aerobic	4451	110	Long slender	Odisha, Bihar, Jharkhand	Short duration; drought tolerant	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 322	Irrigated Late	5450	135–140	Long slender	Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra	–	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 332	Irrigated	5758	135–140	Long bold	Odisha, West Bengal	–	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 804	Rainfed Upland & Shallow Lowland	4800 / 1900	115–120	Long slender	Jharkhand, UP, TN, MP, Chhattisgarh, AP, Telangana	Drought + submergence (MAS)	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 807	Upland	5400 / 2800	105–110	Short bold	Jharkhand, Odisha, Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, AP, TN	Herbicide-tolerant; suitable for DSR	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 808	Upland / Early DSR	3500	90–95	Short bold	Bihar, Jharkhand, Odisha, Assam, Tripura	Drought tolerance (qDTY12.1, qDTY3.1)	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 810	Rainfed Shallow Lowland	4238	150	Short bold	Odisha, WB, Assam	Submergence-tolerant	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack
CR Dhan 811	Rainfed Shallow Lowland	3600	151	Medium slender	Odisha, WB	Submergence-tolerant	ICAR-CRRI, Cuttack

Variety Name	Ecology	Yield (kg/ha) / Stress Yield	Duration (Days)	Grain Type	Recommended States / Regions	Special Trait	Developed By
CSR 101	Aerobic	5500 / 4000	130–135	Long bold	Kerala, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu	Salinity + Bacterial Blight resistance	ICAR-CSSRI, Karnal
DRR Dhan 75	Irrigated	5900	130–135	Medium slender	Telangana, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka, Odisha, Jharkhand, Bihar, Gujarat, Maharashtra	Non-lodging; good grain quality	ICAR-IIRR, Hyderabad
DRR Dhan 77	Irrigated	5020	105–110	Medium slender	Multiple states	–	ICAR-IIRR, Hyderabad
DRR Dhan 79	Irrigated	5500	130–135	Medium slender	Odisha, Punjab, Bihar, MP, Maharashtra, Karnataka	–	ICAR-IIRR, Hyderabad
DRRH-5	Coastal Saline	6500 / 3700	125	Medium slender	WB, Gujarat, Goa, AP	–	ICAR-IIRR, Hyderabad
GR 26	Irrigated	5000	135–140	Long bold	Gujarat	High zinc	NAU, Navsari
KMP-225	Irrigated Mid-Early	6200	120–125	Long bold	Karnataka	–	KSNAUHS, Shimoga
Mahendra Giri	Irrigated Early	3800	115–125	Long slender	Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra, Kerala, Bihar	–	OUAT, Bhubaneswar
Malaviya Manila Sinchit Dhan-1	Irrigated Early	5640 / 3280	115–120	Long slender	Odisha, Bihar	–	BHU, Varanasi
OUAT Kalinga Rice 18	Rainfed Shallow Lowland	5000 / 5500	115–120	Medium slender	Odisha, Bihar, West Bengal	–	OUAT, Bhubaneswar
PR 131	Irrigated	6500	125–130	Long slender	Punjab	–	PAU Ludhiana
Sabour Narendra Dhan	Rainfed Shallow Lowland	4500	110–115	Long slender	Bihar, UP, Chhattisgarh	–	BAU Sabour
Sabour Pratap Dhan	Early Direct-Seeded	5500	130–135	Medium slender	Jharkhand, UP, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Maharashtra, Gujarat, Telangana, Andhra Pradesh	–	BAU Sabour

Variety Name	Ecology	Yield (kg/ha) / Stress Yield	Duration (Days)	Grain Type	Recommended States / Regions	Special Trait	Developed By
Sabour Vijay Dhan	Aerobic	5500	130–135	Medium slender	Bihar, Jharkhand, Chhattisgarh, Karnataka	–	BAU Sabour
Spoorthi	Irrigated Early	5300	125–130	Long bold	Karnataka, AP, TN, Telangana	High zinc (24 ppm)	UAS Raichur
Swarna Purvi Dhan-4	Aerobic	5000	115–120	Long bold	Bihar, Jharkhand, Haryana, Gujarat	–	ICAR-RCER, Patna
Swarna Purvi Dhan-5	Early Direct-Seeded	4500	110–115	Medium slender	Bihar, Jharkhand, WB	–	ICAR-RCER, Patna
TRC 2020-14	Aerobic	5880	120–125	Medium slender	Bihar, Haryana	–	ICAR-NEH, Tripura

3. NOTES

This file acts as **supplemental information** for the article “31 High-Impact IRRI-NARES-Developed Rice Varieties Now Available Across India.” For further details, please refer to the main article available via IRRI.org.